
InChildHealth Workshops in Viennese schools

The project

InChildHealth (www.inchildhealth.eu) is an international research project with 15 partners in 7 countries. We are studying factors of indoor air quality in environments where schoolchildren aged 6 to 13 years spend time. Although many scientific studies have shown that air quality affects health and learning outcomes, there are still many unanswered questions. The Covid-19 pandemic has also highlighted this.

Cities where air measurements will be conducted.

Scientific indoor air quality measurements

In each school and classroom, measurement devices will be set up for two weeks during the summer semester of 2024 to measure air quality. Additionally, monthly samples for microbiological analysis will be collected using dust collectors, and three monthly samples will be taken for chemical analysis. This will allow us to gather data on particulate matter, temperature, relative humidity, volatile organic compounds, CO₂, CO, NO₂, formaldehyde, bacteria, and fungi. Furthermore, the materials used in the school and environmental parameters (e.g., number of windows, building materials, furniture materials, cleaning products) will be recorded, and as part of a master's thesis, bacteria and fungi will be measured in different locations within the school building.

The workshops

It is important to us to actively involve the students in the project. Therefore, we are conducting workshops at five schools in Vienna, where the children can learn about air quality. At small laboratory stations, they can try out the work of the researchers. Additionally, the students will help describe their classrooms and identify aspects that may influence indoor air quality. As part of small, self-directed scientific inquiries, the students will collect samples in their school building and analyze them together with the researcher. Furthermore, through Citizen Science activities, the students can also take electrostatic dust collectors home to measure the biological air quality in their own living spaces.

Students will fill out a questionnaire before and after their participation in the Citizen Science activities, which will anonymously assess the impact of the workshop on their knowledge and interest regarding research and indoor air quality. This anonymous questionnaire will also ask for the students' age, gender, and student number.

Consent

For your child to participate in filling out the questionnaires, we ask for your consent. Your child will receive the consent form to be signed as a separate sheet from the teaching staff to take home.

Optional ways of participation

In addition to participating in the school workshops, there are two more options for those who are more interested in the topic of 'indoor air quality'.

Option1: Indoor air measurement at home

For five students and their parents or legal guardians, there is an opportunity to participate in indoor air measurement in their own homes. Devices for measuring air quality will be set up in the homes of interested participants. The measurements will take place twice in 2024: once for one week in the spring (around March 2024) and once for one week in the summer (around June 2024). Parents or legal guardians will also be asked to complete a questionnaire. This will gather information about aspects that could influence indoor air quality in the home, such as the materials used for walls and floors, as well as factors that may affect outdoor air quality.

Additionally, upon request, a microbiological measurement can be conducted in the five selected homes, where all rooms will be checked for possible bacteria and fungi (duration approximately one hour). The participants will personally receive the results of these measurements within two weeks after the samples are collected.

Option 2: Mobile measurements

Up to 100 students have the opportunity to use mobile measurements devices to study how air quality changes in their surroundings over the course of a day. For this, students can carry a portable device with them for four days. The mobile devices are designed with a shoulder strap for easy transport, allowing students to easily take them along during their daily activities. To connect the collected air quality data with the students' locations (e.g., air quality on the way to school, air quality at the playground, etc.), students will be asked to keep a diary. In this diary, they can record their activities by location with simple entries at the end of each day.

As in Option 1, the parents or legal guardians of the students will be asked to describe aspects of the home that may influence indoor air quality in a questionnaire. This questionnaire will also ask about known health conditions of the students, such as asthma, allergies, and respiratory issues. The results of the measurements will also be anonymized for participants and personally delivered by the researchers. More information on participating in these measurements will be provided to interested children and parents or legal guardians in an online seminar organized in the spring of 2024.

Would you like to know more?

If you and your child would like to participate in one or both options, please send a brief message to the teaching staff. All interested parties will be gathered by the teaching staff and will receive further information as well as an additional consent form for this part of the project.

Contact person

AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH: DI Clara-E. Pogner (clara.pogner@ait.ac.at), M +43 664 2351758

ZSI – Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GmbH: Mag. Teresa Schaefer (schaefer@zsi.at), Dr. Claudia Magdalena Fabian (fabian@zsi.at), Dr. Barbara Kieslinger (kieslinger@zsi.at)

Data Protection

All data is collected solely for the purpose of conducting the scientific study. The data will be anonymized as soon as possible. The basis for data processing is Articles 9, 13, and 14 of the GDPR.

The researchers at AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH are supported in data management by a Data Protection Officer, Christof Hetzmanseder, who can be contacted at dpo@ait.ac.at. The researchers at the Center for Social Innovation GmbH are supported in data management by an ethics committee. You can contact the Data Protection Officers at ZSI via dpo@zsi.at.

The collected personal data is stored in such a way that unauthorized persons cannot access it. The retention period for this data is in accordance with the statutory limitation periods and is a maximum of 10 years after the end of the project.

The responsible parties for the processing of personal data are:

AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH (AIT)

Giefinggasse 4, 1210 Wien

Email: office@ait.ac.at

Webseite: www.ait.ac.at

ZSI - Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GmbH:

Linke Wienzeile 246, 1150 Wien

Tel.: +43-1-495 04 42-41

Email: dpo@zsi.at

Webseite: www.zsi.at

For questions and information regarding data protection, please contact the Data Protection Officer at ZSI at dpo@zsi.at.

Type, Scope, and Origin of Collected Data

As part of this project, AIT and ZSI collect personal data directly. We only collect personal data necessary for carrying out the “InChildHealth” project (www.inchildhealth.at), adhering to the principle of data minimization.

AIT and ZSI collect and process the following:

- Your name (consent form)
- Your child’s name (consent form)
- Your child’s age
- Your child’s gender
- Your child’s student number
- GPS data collected by air quality measuring devices, if applicable (mobile measurements)
- All information shared by you or your child via the questionnaire

You have the right to request information about the personal data stored about you. Furthermore, you have the right to have data corrected or deleted. Under the specific conditions of the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR), you are also entitled to request the restriction of the processing of your data or its transfer. Additionally, you have the right to object to the processing of your data.

If your data is processed based on your consent, you can withdraw this consent at any time. The withdrawal of consent does not affect the legality of the processing up to the point of withdrawal. If you wish to exercise your rights, please contact: clara.pogner@ait.ac.at, dpo@ait.ac.at.

If you believe that the processing of your personal data violates the GDPR, you may file a complaint with a supervisory authority, either in the place of your employment or where the alleged infringement took place.

The supervisory authority responsible for us is:

Österreichische Datenschutzbehörde

Barichgasse 40-42, 1030 Wien

Tel.: +43-1-52 152-0

Email: dsb@dsb.gv.at